

ELASTIC-PLASTIC FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF HYBRID SHORT FIBER+PARTICLE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Micromechanical modeling of heterogeneous materials, including discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs), continues to play a substantial role in the development of new materials systems [1-4]. Numerical analysis for micromechanical modeling seems to be well suited to describe the behaviors of these composites. Above all, the use of representative volume element (RVE) [1,2] or unit cell [3,4] of the composite microstructure, together with finite element analysis tool is well established for the investigation of effective material properties and/or to understand micromechanics of the composite materials. RVE modeling should be typical of the whole composite microstructure and contains a sufficient number of inclusions for the apparent overall properties to be effectively independent of the boundary condition [1-4].

On the other hand, magnesium MMCs are attractive materials for applications such as automotive cylinder blocks, piston rings and disk brakes due to their high specific modulus, excellent wear resistance and stiffness. In particular, Hybrid MMCs reinforced have attracted more attention than single reinforced MMCs. In the hybrid MMCs, the reinforcement is produced by a combination of short ceramic fibers and particles. Since short fiber type reinforcements generally improve tensile strength and modulus of the MMCs and particle type reinforcements generally increase their wear resistance, the hybrid MMCs enables the desired properties to be obtained by the appropriate combination of ceramic reinforcements [5-7]. They also have been recommended as an effective and economic alternative to conventional high-cost short fiber or whisker reinforced products [8].

Since the mechanical properties of the hybrid MMCs are critically determined by shapes, volume fractions and sizes of fibers and particles as well as interactions between them, a detailed understanding of the microstructure-property relationships are required for their engineering applications. In the present work, three-dimensional finite element models were developed to study the micromechanics during deformation of the hybrid short fiber + particle reinforced MMCs. RVEs of three different microstructures of MMCs were reconstructed using modified random sequential adsorption algorithm, and their tensile deformation behaviors were analyzed using finite element method. Then the numerical results obtained from the models were compared with experimental tensile test results of MMCs.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Materials

Three types of magnesium MMCs were investigated. The matrix was commercial AZ91 magnesium alloy and reinforcements were Saffil ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$, diameter of $3.5\mu\text{m}$ and length of $70\mu\text{m}$) and SiC particles (diameters of 7 and $20\mu\text{m}$). Table 1 represents volume fractions of Saffil and SiC used for the investigations. Sample A consisted of monolithic Saffil fiber with a volume fraction of 20%. Samples B and C consisted of 15% Saffil fiber and 5% SiC particles with different particle sizes of 7 and $20\mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Magnesium MMCs were fabricated by squeeze infiltration method. This method encompasses pressure-assisted liquid infiltration of a porous preform. Before infiltration take place, the reinforcement preform has prepared by the press forming. And then the preform is placed in a mold,

and the liquid Mg alloy is poured into a preheated die located on the bed of a hydraulic press.

2.2 Numerical modeling

In order to investigate the mechanical properties of randomly reinforced MMCs, RVEs were generated using a modified random sequential adsorption algorithm. The volume elements used here were cubic periodic boxes (length $L=45\mu\text{m}$). In the algorithm, the short fibers and particles were sequentially added into a periodic cubic space by randomly generating the center point and orientation. To analyze the models considered, Static Structural (ANSYS) software was used. The matrix, short fibers and particles were meshed with ten-node quadratic tetrahedral elements (SOLID 187), which were generated by sweeping the corresponding 2D meshes on the top surface of each short fiber. The number of node and elements were about 91000 and 200000, respectively. The short fiber was modeled with Young's modulus of 300 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.2, and particle also was modeled with Young's modulus of 400 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.2. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the squeeze casted AZ91 alloy were 45GPa and 0.35, respectively. The thermal residual stresses, which were induced by the cooling process after casting, were also modeled using $\Delta T=628^\circ\text{C}$ ($650^\circ\text{C}-22^\circ\text{C}$).

To predict tensile deformation behavior of MMCs, a uniaxial tensile strain was applied to the RVE model by fixing the displacement of the y-z plane in the x-direction, and applying an x-direction displacement on the opposite side of the model. The rotation of the model was constrained along all three axes to prevent shear deformation of the present non-uniform RVE model. This processing repeats y and z-direction, respectively. The mechanical properties of RVE model were estimated by the average of x, y and z-direction.

3 Results and Discussion

Fig.1(a), (b) and (c) show SEM images of MMCs. For all three samples, the Saffil short fibers and SiC particles were distributed uniformly in the matrix using squeeze infiltration method. RVE models geometry and meshes were shown in Fig.1(d), (e) and (f). RVEs using modified random sequential adsorption algorithm also were reconstructed

uniform and similar microstructures to the experimental MMCs.

For composites, the plastic deformation of matrix is mainly initiated at matrix/reinforcements interface, where the reinforcements were located close to each other. Because, initiated plastic deformation called microplasticity has been attributed to stress concentrations in the matrix [9]. The equivalent plastic strain fields of models with tensile stress of 100MPa were shown in Fig.2. The white area is reinforcements which are short fibers and particles. The plastic deformation of matrix was concentrated around reinforcements. Especially, the deformation was uniformly distributed in Sample A and Sample B, whereas the deformation of Sample C was concentrated and widely spread around particle.

Table 2 represents the comparison of yield strength between the predicted results using finite element analysis and investigated ones by experiments. The results of RVEs and experimental MMCs are almost similar. However, the predicted yield strength of Sample C was higher than experimental result of Sample C. The reason of results is that ductility decreases with increasing particle size [9]. Therefore, finite element analysis was executed in non-fracture state, whereas experimental MMC with large particle size was fractured before whole plastic deformation. A brittle fracture of Sample C was proved in Fig.3. Yield strength and tensile strength of Sample C was shown a same result. It also showed tensile strength of Sample A such as short fiber single reinforced MMC was more excellent than Sample B and Sample C, and tensile strength of small particle was more excellent than large size particle.

In spite of the above analyses, the exact reason for the observed low tensile strength of hybrid short fiber + particle reinforced MMCs are not completely clear. Further investigations need to be considered.

4 Conclusions

The micromechanical deformation behavior of short fiber + particle hybrid MMCs was investigated using FE analysis tool and RVE model.

- (1) RVE models using modified random sequential adsorption algorithm were reconstructed uniform and similar microstructures to the MMCs. Moreover, yield strength of RVEs corresponded well to the results of experimental

MMCs.

(2) Hybrid MMCs with 20um particle fractured before plastic deformation in accordance with concentrated plastic deformation around particle.

(3) Tensile strength of short fiber single reinforced MMCs were more excellent than short

fiber + particle hybrid reinforced MMCs in same volume fraction. In hybrid MMCs, tensile strength of 7um particle hybrid MMCs were more excellent than 20um particle hybrid MMCs.

Table 1. Volume fractions of short fibers and particles of the MMCs used for the investigation.

	Saffil short fiber	SiC particle (7 μm)	SiC particle (20 μm)
Sample A	20vol.%	-	-
Sample B	15vol.%	5vol.%	-
Sample C	15vol.%	-	5vol.%

Fig.1. SEM images of fabricated magnesium MMCs of (a) Sample A, (b) Sample B and (c) Sample C using squeeze infiltration method and RVE models geometry and meshes of (d) Sample A, (e) Sample B and (f) Sample C.

Fig.2. Equivalent plastic strain fields on a 2-D cross section of (a) Sample A, (b) Sample B and (c) Sample C with tensile stress of 100MPa

Table 2. The comparison of yield strength between the predicted results using finite element analysis and experimental results.

	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C
RVEs	156 MPa	140 MPa	166 MPa
Experiment	154MPa	142MPa	144MPa

Fig.3. Tensile strength of experimental MMCs.

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